

CRISPR/Cas system research has advanced significantly in biological sciences. There are still many challenges to effective delivery before efficient gene editing may be achieved

Moataz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia.

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia

Abstract- The CRISPR/Cas system's discovery and execution offer great promise for the treatment of human illnesses and the revolutionization of plant breeding. Despite the fact that CRISPR/Cas system research is well advanced in the life sciences community, there are still considerable barriers to effective delivery that must be overcome before effective gene editing can be achieved. Consider characteristics like specificity, efficacy, and controlled expression while deciding on a plan. Due to the discovery of innovative delivery systems, many of the shortcomings of the CRISPR/Cas system's translatability have been addressed. Because of the rapid growth of delivery mechanisms, a successful translation of CRISPR/Cas technology into medical and agricultural applications is vital, and substantial progress is predicted

I. INTRODUCTION

Gene editing has made it possible to precisely modify particular genomic areas in a wide range of species. The majority of gene editing is done with highly specialized programmable nucleases. Double-strand breaks (DSBs) are created by these nucleases in genomic areas of interest. These DSBs are subsequently repaired using either error-prone nonhomologous end-joining (NHEJ) or error-free homology-directed repair (HDR); specific alterations, like as insertions or deletions (indels), are subsequently inserted into chosen sections of the genome (1,2,3). The faults in genes may be addressed by adding HDR repair template, offering promise for repairing innate DNA mistakes.

The clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated (Cas)-type II RNA-guided nucleases system (4), a relatively novel programmable nuclease technology, has transformed the scientific area of gene editing. Despite the variety and ease of construction and target design that make CRISPR/Cas so appealing for breakthrough gene therapy and crop enhancement, there are still significant drawbacks to consider (5, 6). The immunological response in animal systems is one of the challenges; because the CRISPR/Cas system's components are bacterially generated, the system is likely to induce host immunological responses. Another stumbling block is the size of the system's components, which are all macromolecules. As a result, they are unable to reach the cytoplasm and subsequently the nucleus on their own (6, which is required for effective gene modification (7). Furthermore, the CRISPR/Cas system's huge size may make it challenging to bundle into delivery vehicles like viral vectors. Another facet of the CRISPR/Cas system's difficulty is its stability. Otherwise, the CRISPR/Cas system will be destroyed or destroyed during circulation in the targeted organs or tissues. One of the remaining big challenges in CRISPR/Cas-mediated gene editing is efficient delivery. As a result, building robust and effective distribution methods is essential for its implementation. The methods for delivering the CRISPR/Cas system to diverse biological systems, including animals, aquacultures, and plants, were covered in this review.

II. THE GENE-EDITING TECHNOLOGY CRISPR/CAS

The CRISPR/Cas system was discovered as a bacterial adaptive immune system for the first time. It was the first programmed nuclease system discovered to act as ribonucleoprotein particles and detect their targets through base pairing (8). Because it is very straightforward to redesign to generate target specificity, this gene editing technique has been widely employed. CRISPR/Cas has been created and developed by scientists to function as an effective gene-editing tool (4).

The tracrRNA, Cas9 protein, and pre-crRNA are the three main components of the CRISPR/Cas9 system. After transcription, tracrRNA joins

pre-crRNA to create a complex. The Cas9 protein stabilizes the complex, and RNase III processes the pre-crRNA to produce crRNA (9). The protospacer adjacent motif (PAM), which is a short motif situated adjacent to the target DNA sequence, is recognized by the Cas9/gRNA complex (made up of crRNA and tracrRNA). The complex then begins unwinding the target DNA at the seed region (10–12 nucleotides) (11). Cas9's two nuclease domains break the target strands when the DNA sequence matches the gRNA (12,13,14). Single or multiple mismatches can be allowed by the Cas9/gRNA complex, with mismatches downstream of the seed region being tolerated more commonly (13, 15).

There are six different kinds of CRISPR/Cas systems (types I–VI) that are further divided into two classes: class 1 and class 2 CRISPR/Cas systems (16, 17). The key distinguishing feature of the class 1 CRISPR/Cas system, which is divided into types I, III, and IV, is the presence of several effector nuclease complexes. The class 2 CRISPR/Cas system varies from the class 1 system in that it only requires a single effector nuclease; type II, V, and VI are subclasses of class 2. Nucleic acid detection and genome engineering are possible because of their programmable single effector nucleases (3, 18,19,20,21). Cas9, Cas12, and Cas13 effectors are used in Types II, V, and VI (22,23,24). The CRISPR/Cas9 system is the most widely utilized among them yet.

III. THE CRISPR/CAS TECHNOLOGY IS BEING USED TO MODIFY GENES.

Cas nuclease activity-based strategies

Various gene editing techniques for DNA (gene destruction, precise repair, targeted insertion, large-scale DNA editing) and RNA modification have been developed based on CRISPR/Cas nuclease activity.

Editing of DNA

NHEJ ligates DSBs created by Cas endonuclease for gene disruption, and this break-and-repair process repeats until the target sequence is changed and an indel arises (25). Frameshifting or exon skipping can occur as a result of an indel, resulting in gene disruption. By destroying the mutant allele while keeping the normal allele, gene disruption can also mute dominant negative mutations. HDR also inserts a donor template with homology arms into the genome to match the target region to the genome and produce a loss (26).

HDR employs a donor template with the required insertion or mutation for accurate repair. This donor template features homology arms that allow it to precisely match the target region and insert genetic material or change the genome (25).

HDR permits accurate insertion of exogenous DNA sequences into the genomes of dividing cells, whereas homology-independent targeted integration (HITI) uses an NHEJ-based homology-independent method to insert exogenous DNA sequences into the genomes of nondividing cells (27).

DNA fragments can be eliminated by using the CRISPR/Cas system with two guide RNAs that target distinct locations for large-scale DNA editing (editing a size of up to several megabase pairs (Mbp)). Allelic exchange can also be used to treat recessive compound heterozygous mutations. This is accomplished by causing homologous DNA breaks on both chromosomes, and allelic exchange between mutant alleles can help to reverse the illness phenotype (28).

Editing of RNA

The CRISPR/Cas system works on both DNA and RNA. Previous research has identified the psiRNA-Cmr protein complex, which consists of prokaryotic silencing (psi) RNAs and Cmr Cas proteins, as an RNA-targeting CRISPR/Cas effector complex. Prokaryotes have their own RNA silencing mechanism, as this complex cleaves target RNAs at a specified place (29). ssRNA targets have also been demonstrated to bind to and cleave by Cas endonuclease (30). Strutt et al. demonstrated that type II-A and II-C Cas9 endonucleases may recognize and cleave ssRNA without the need for a PAM. (31.) The RNA-editing Cas13 family was recently identified by scientists. The Cas13 family has been discovered to be a programmable CRISPR/Cas system for RNA editing. This technique is more selective and efficient than prior RNA targeting techniques (32,33,34). Cas13d was recently found in *Ruminococcus flavefaciens* XPD3002 (CasRx) by Konermann et al., and it has great activity in human cells. CasRx is a tiny protein of 930 amino acids that may be packed into an adeno-associated virus (AAV) in a variety of ways, making it ideal for distribution using AAV vectors. In addition to its knockdown action, catalytically inactivated CasRx may be used as a splice effector to modulate pre-mRNA splicing (35).

Cas-effector fusion protein activity-based strategies

Because CRISPR/Cas has DNA-binding characteristics, it might be useful in a variety of applications beyond site-specific gene editing. To regulate gene expression, a catalytically dead Cas9 enzyme (dCas9) was designed (36). dCas9, like Cas9, may recognize and attach to a DNA sequence of interest. dCas9 has been employed for transcriptional suppression, transcriptional activation, imparting epigenetic alterations, and base editing, rather than cleaving the target DNA sequence. By fusing dCas9 to gene activators, repressors, acetyltransferases, or adenosine deaminases, these activities can be achieved. Because dCas9 is in a catalytically inactive state, it is employed for precision targeting rather than catalysis.

Transcriptional regulation dCas9 can be fused with transcriptional repressors or activators to target the promoter region of a gene of interest

and cause transcriptional repression (CRISPR interference) or activation (CRISPR activation) without changing the genome; this activity has been demonstrated in *Escherichia coli*, plant, and mammalian cells (36,37,38). Furthermore, investigations have demonstrated that a modifying sgRNA can improve transcriptional regulatory specificity. For example, sequence-specific transcriptional activation may be achieved by combining the Cas9-VP64 transcriptional activator with a sgRNA containing two MS2 RNA aptamer hairpin sequences (39).

The CRISPR/Cas system can also be used to modify epigenetics. Hilton et al. combined dCas9 with an acetyltransferase that catalyzes histone H3 acetylation at lysine 27. Specific gene expression has been demonstrated to be substantially activated by this modulation. This method may be used to achieve not just acetylation but also methylation (40).

CRISPR/dCas has been used for precision DNA base editing and prime editing. Komor et al. created the CRISPR/nickase Cas9 (nCas9)-based base editor, which was utilized to transform a specific C–G base pair to T–A via a DNA cytosine deaminase (41). Gaudelli et al. produced a transfer RNA adenosine deaminase that can convert A–T base pairs to G–C base pairs when coupled to nCas9 (42). Because single point mutations account for a major category of genetic illnesses, this type of CRISPR/Cas-mediated editing is effective.

Prime editing, a more powerful and versatile gene-editing method recently discovered as a way to introduce indels and enable base conversions in both transitions and transversions (43), has recently been discovered as a way to introduce indels and enable base conversions in both transitions and transversions. Prime editor is the name given to the editor used in prime editing. The primary editor is a combination of nCas9 and reverse transcriptase. A primary editing gRNA directs the primary editor (pegRNA). The pegRNA attaches to a single strand DNA (ssDNA) and triggers reverse transcription when nCas9 nicks the target region. After that, the reverse transcribed pegRNA is inserted into the target location.

Current methods for delivering the CRISPR/Cas system in mammals. CRISPR/Cas can be administered by DNA, RNA, or protein, among other modalities. Cas and gRNA are supplied as a single plasmid when administered in DNA mode. Cas mRNA is supplied with a distinct gRNA in the RNA manner. Cas protein is supplied as a ribonucleoprotein complex with gRNA in the protein mode (RNP). Each technique is generally useful, although it does have certain drawbacks. The delivered cargo is more stable when Cas9 and gRNA are packaged together in the same plasmid than when they are delivered separately. However, the large size of the plasmid increases the difficulty of delivery, and plasmid integration into the host genome and prolonged expression are potential limitations of this delivery method. Cas9 mRNA delivery allows for speedier gene editing. However, because RNA is fragile, gRNA degradation may occur before Cas9 mRNA is effectively translated. For gene editing, the RNP is the most direct and quickest method. However, obtaining a pure protein is significantly more difficult than plasmids or mRNAs. Furthermore, the injection of bacterial proteins unexpectedly may trigger an immunological response in the host.

There are two types of delivery vehicles: viral vectors and nonviral vectors. Viral vectors are the predominant vehicle for delivering CRISPR/Cas in vivo. Nonviral vector delivery has not been as widely employed as viral vector delivery so far. Nonviral vectors, on the other hand, are equivalent to viral vectors and are a hot focus of research.

CRISPR/Cas gene editing and delivery via viruses

Viral vectors are frequently employed to deliver gene-editing materials such as DNA. Lentivirus, adenovirus, and AAV are three kinds of viral vectors often employed for CRISPR/Cas gene delivery. Despite the great effectiveness of viral distribution in vivo, there are several drawbacks, including safety concerns. After infection, these viruses release the viral genome into the host cells. This necessitates strong connections between the virus and the host cells; as a result, viral delivery methods are more difficult than most nonviral approaches in vivo.

Lentivirus is a kind of lentivirus.

Lentiviruses are RNA viruses that may replicate in both proliferating and non-dividing cells. Lentiviruses are a great way to get a message to cells that are difficult to transfect with chemical approaches. It also has a big packing capacity of 10.7 kilobytes (44). This characteristic enables it to contain numerous sgRNA sequences, each of which can cause numerous gene edits at the same time (45). Lentiviruses have been utilized in many early gene-editing research because of these benefits. Lentivirus administration has been used to create mouse models of myeloid malignancy (46) and lung cancer (47). However, there are also drawbacks to utilizing lentivirus, such as the incorporation of the viral genome, which has been linked to cancer (48).

To address these concerns, lentiviral vectors have been modified to become integration-deficient lentiviral vectors (IDLVs), which minimize the viral genome's unwanted integration into the host cell genome (49, 50). IDLVs maintain the ability to alter genes in difficult-to-transfect cells (51, 52). Despite the fact that IDLVs have been discovered to generate undesirable gene changes, the study also discovered that due to their active engagement of host HDR proteins, IDLVs exhibit excellent site-specific gene repair activities (53). As a result, combining IDLVs with safer endonucleases like SpCas9-HF or eSpCas9 might boost their utility (54, 55).

Adenovirus is a kind of virus.

Adenoviruses are viruses with double-stranded DNA (dsDNA). Adenoviruses, like lentiviruses, may infect both proliferating and nondividing

cells. Adenoviruses, on the other hand, do not typically promote genome integration in host DNA, therefore they do not have the same potential for off-target consequences as lentiviruses. The effective editing of the *Pcsk9* (proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9) and *Pten* (phosphatase and tensin homolog) genes in adult mouse liver has been demonstrated using an adenovirus-based delivery of the CRISPR/Cas system (56, 57). Furthermore, adenovirus-based administration has been utilized to successfully induce specific chromosomal rearrangements in vivo to develop EML4-ALK-driven lung cancer in echinoderm microtubule-associated protein like 4-anaplastic lymphoma kinase (EML4-ALK)-deficient mice (58).

Adenoviruses, on the other hand, can provoke a strong immunological response. Adenoviruses are extremely expensive and difficult to mass-produce in large quantities. These drawbacks limit the use of adenovirus-mediated gene delivery in clinical gene therapy (56).

Adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) are ssDNA viruses with a modest size. AAV-based administration is safer and more efficient than lentivirus and adenovirus-based administration because it causes very modest cytotoxicity and immunological responses (59, 60). AAVs come in a variety of serotypes, which allow for a wide range of tissue tropisms and effective gene editing (61). In the mouse brain, for example, Swiech et al. reported the first effective AAV-based CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing (62). Hung et al. employed a similar strategy for retinal gene editing in adult mice and produced strong editing results (63). Successful AAV-based CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing in the retina of retinal degeneration mice models has also been reported (64, 65). CRISPR/Cas components delivered by AAV have also been employed to knockdown IGF in the central nervous system (66). Furthermore, studies have shown that muscle tissue-specific delivery of CRISPR/Cas components through AAV vectors may fix a mutant dystrophin gene in Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), with functional recovery in vivo (61, 67,68,69). Using a self-complementary AAV (scAAV) approach, Zhang et al. recently reported increased CRISPR-Cas9-mediated gene-editing efficiency in a DMD mouse model (70). In newborn mice with metabolic liver illness, AAV-based CRISPR/Cas9 delivery was also employed to produce successful gene repair (71, 72). Furthermore, by delivering sgRNAs using AAVs in a tissue-specific SpCas9 transgenic mouse, illness animal models such as cardiomyopathy (73) and lung cancer (74) may be generated. Murlidharan et al. also employed chimeric AAV (AAV2g9) to transport gRNAs targeting the schizophrenia risk gene *MIR137* into the brain of a CRISPR/Cas9 knock-in mouse model, resulting in gene loss localized to the brain (75). Furthermore, utilizing AAVs to deliver sgRNAs into CRISPR/Cas9 knock-in mice, high-throughput mutagenesis may be exploited to construct autochthonous cancer animal models (76, 77). Despite advances in employing AAVs for CRISPR/Cas-based gene editing, AAVs' modest cargo capacity (4.7 kb) may limit their use. As a result, another vector system is frequently necessary when combining ordinary SpCas9, which has a size of 4.2 kb, with the inclusion of sgRNA. Later, scientists produced numerous smaller Cas9 orthologs (such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (SaCas9) (78), *Campylobacter jejuni* (CjCas9) (79), *Streptococcus thermophilus* (StCas9) (80), and *Neisseria meningitidis* (NmCas9) (79)) to allow in vivo gene editing with a single AAV vector.

IV. CRISPR/CAS GENE EDITING AND DELIVERY WITHOUT THE USE OF VIRUSES

Because DNA is more stable than RNA, it is widely employed to introduce the CRISPR/Cas system into cells. CRISPR/Cas-encoding DNA allows for more efficient gene editing than previous approaches (81,82,83). The CRISPR/Cas9 components, for example, were supplied in the form of DNA to a mouse model of tyrosinemia through tail-vein hydrodynamic injection and accomplished > 6 percent gene correction in the liver cells after a single administration (84).

In addition, Zhen et al. found that hydrodynamic injection of CRISPR/Cas9-encoding DNA may effectively stop the hepatitis B virus from replicating by causing mutations in viral DNA (85). In addition to systemic treatment, subretinal injection of CRISPR/Cas components in plasmid form combined with electroporation has been reported to enable allele-specific gene editing in the retina of a rat model of retinitis pigmentosa (86). In a mouse model of retinitis pigmentosa, Latella et al. discovered a similar effect, which greatly lowered mutant protein levels and averted substantial visual impairment (87). Li et al. also achieved allele-specific gene editing in the retinas of Rho-P23H knock-in mice (88), which targeted the P23H allele with a single-nucleotide alteration. Shinmyo et al. also used in utero electroporation to transfer a plasmid containing CRISPR/Cas components into the mouse brain for successful brain-specific gene editing in vivo (89). These studies proved the viability of CRISPR/Cas9 delivery through DNA in vivo.

Deliveries based on RNA

The danger of host genome integration is greatly reduced using RNA-based delivery techniques. However, the effective period of RNA-based delivery systems is rather short, and such delivery systems have certain additional drawbacks. The stability of RNA, as well as the requirement to supply the components (Cas mRNA and sgRNA) individually, are two of the method's primary problems. Yin et al. presented a technique for delivering CRISPR/Cas9 components that included lipid nanoparticles delivering Cas9 mRNA and an AAV delivering the sgRNA/HDR template. They successfully corrected the *Fah* (fumarylacetoacetate hydrolase) gene in a mouse type of hereditary tyrosinemia using this technique (90). It is crucial to note, however, that this combined strategy still requires viral codelivery to reach a certain level of efficiency, because RNA is more unstable than DNA and protein. Furthermore, sgRNA degradation may have a major impact on editing efficiency. To boost the effectiveness of these approaches, more study into improving sgRNA stability is needed. The stability of sgRNA can be improved by altering it, according to studies. Yin et al. changed the 2'OH group of sgRNA to 2'OMe and 2'F, as well as adding phosphorothioate linkages (91). This work found that a single injection increased the effectiveness of editing *Pcsk9* in the livers of mice by more than 80%, showing a possible improved strategy for enhancing RNA stability and overcoming the challenges of RNA-based delivery. Other researchers published a

work in which modified sgRNA and Cas9-encoding mRNA were bundled in a lipid nanoparticle carrier. The mouse Ttr (transthyretin) gene was reduced by more than 97 percent in the serum protein levels of the liver after a single treatment. This study (92) exhibited effective gene editing that lasted at least a year. Another work used a lipid nanoparticle containing disulfide bonds (BAMEA-O16B) to transport Cas9 mRNA and sgRNA in vivo and exhibited a high editing effectiveness (80%) (93).

Delivery based on proteins

The fastest and most direct approach for gene editing is to deliver Cas protein with gRNA as a Cas9 RNP, which is appropriate for in vivo therapeutic applications. A fusion protein comprising Cas9 and negatively supercharged proteins was designed to allow transport of Cas9 RNPs into target cells using cationic lipid based transfection reagents like RNAiMAX (94). The Cas9 RNP/RNAiMAX combination was injected into the cochlea of Atoh1 (atonal bHLH transcription factor 1)-GFP mice, resulting in a 13% drop in GFP in the transgenic mice ears. Mangeot et al. developed nanoblades, a vector based on the murine leukemia virus (MLV) for delivering Cas9 RNPs for in vivo gene editing (95). Furthermore, an amphiphilic nanocomplex was created to distribute Cas9 RNPs in vivo and demonstrated efficient gene editing in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease (96). PEI polymers or mixed PEI polymers with liposomes were also employed for Cas9 RNP administration in vivo to improve endosomal escape. To transport Cas9 RNPs into the nucleus of human cells, Sun et al. coated a DNA nanoclew with PEI polymers. Target gene disruption may be accomplished with this vehicle without compromising cell viability (97). The researchers also found that changing the DNA nanoclew to be partly complimentary with the sgRNA can improve the editing efficiency even further. Furthermore, Cas9 protein modification can boost the effectiveness of direct cytoplasmic/nuclear transport of Cas9 RNP. Mout et al. created the Cas9En protein, which has a negatively charged oligo glutamic acid tag linked to the N-terminus of the Cas9 protein (98). Cas9En RNPs were administered utilizing positively charged arginine-functionalized gold nanoparticles (Arg-AuNPs). Cas9 RNPs were transported straight to the cytosol, accumulated in the nucleus, and gave a 30 percent editing efficiency with the NLS attached. This nano-assembled technology was recently employed for Cas9 RNP delivery in vivo, with a gene editing efficiency of > 8% (99).

In disease models, AuNPs have also been employed to distribute Cas9 RNPs in vivo for gene editing and repair. AuNPs may be combined with donor DNA, Cas9 RNPs, and the endosomal disruptive polymer poly (N-(N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-aminoethyl)-2-aminoethyl) aspartamide) (PAsp (DET) to create a CRISPR-Gold vehicle. CRISPR-Gold-based Cas9 RNPs delivery may repair the dystrophin gene in the muscle tissue of DMD mice by 5.4 percent, according to Lee et al. (100). Another study (101) found that injecting CRISPR-Gold into the brain saved mice from developing aberrant behaviors induced by fragile X syndrome. While improved endosomal escape is still necessary for improved delivery efficiency, CRISPR-Gold may provide an opportunity in the development of therapeutic techniques targeting muscle and brain illnesses. In comparison to DNA and RNA-based delivery, protein-based delivery has less off-target effects and a lower immune response (102). Cas9 RNPs improve effectiveness by preventing sgRNA degradation. Cas9 RNP trafficking into the cytosol or nucleus, on the other hand, is crucial for therapeutic effects. As a result, endosomal entrapment remains a significant challenge (103).

In aquaculture, the current method of distributing the CRISPR/Cas system

The CRISPR/Cas system has effectively edited the genomes of various aquaculture species, including zebrafish, Atlantic salmon, Nile tilapia, sea bream, catfish, carp, rainbow trout, Northern Chinese lamprey, and Pacific oyster. CRISPR/Cas gene editing procedures established in model species like zebrafish have been used in aquaculture species (104). Microinjection is the most common technique of gene transfer in aquaculture species. Microinjection is a technique of gene editing that involves injecting the CRISPR/Cas complex into newly fertilized eggs using specialized equipment (105). NHEJ was utilized to produce mutations in the majority of instances, although HDR has been effectively employed in rohu carp (106). However, mosaicism might emerge if gene editing is continued at different phases of embryonic development. These issues are the subject of current research, which aims to make CRISPR/Cas technology more widely adopted in aquaculture. Sterility, growth, and disease resistance of aquaculture species have all been addressed using CRISPR/Cas approaches. The goal of producing sterility in fish is to restrict gene transfer between domesticated strains. CRISPR/Cas approaches, for example, have been used to make Atlantic salmon sterile (107). Several articles have shown that utilizing the CRISPR/Cas method, gene editing of the myostatin gene can improve the development of fish such as channel catfish and common carp (108, 109). Immunity and disease resistance in channel catfish, rohu carp, and grass carp have also been studied using the CRISPR/Cas method (106, 110, 111). The tlr22 gene was disrupted in rohu carp, resulting in a model for researching immunology and proving the capacity of CRISPR/Cas to help in the development of successful aquaculture therapies. It is feasible to build disease resistance, reduce illness incidence, and increase species resilience in aquaculture by understanding the underlying processes of transcription and translation using CRISPR/Cas-based techniques. For a variety of reasons, aquaculture is an excellent candidate for CRISPR/Cas gene editing. Thousands of externally fertilized eggs enable microinjection by hand, allowing for enormous sample volumes without incurring high expenditures. The huge sample size ensures objectivity and is important for comparing successfully altered samples to controls and determining pathogen resistance. Furthermore, because comprehensive phenotypes are feasible, a high sample size allows for the construction of well-developed disease challenge models. It is getting simpler to research gene function, increase disease resistance, and produce new strains with specific features that might boost economic value as aquaculture technology matures.

The current method for introducing the CRISPR/Cas system to plants is as follows:

As previously demonstrated, the CRISPR/Cas technology is extremely effective in altering animal genomes. Its capacity to alter plant genomes has also been established in studies. To express the CRISPR/Cas system in plants, a mixed dual promoter system is typically utilized. RNA

polymerase II promoters are utilized to express Cas protein, whereas RNA polymerase III promoters specific to plants, such as AtU6 for Arabidopsis or tomato, TaU6 for wheat, and OsU6 or OsU3 for rice, are utilized to express gRNA in mixed dual promoter systems (112,113,114,115).

However, effective transport of the CRISPR/Cas9 system into cells is required to use CRISPR/Cas9 technology to create novel characteristics in plants. In plants, there are two types of delivery methods: indirect and direct. Plant bacteria or viruses are used to mediate the introduction of DNA constructs into target plant cells through indirect techniques (such as agroinfiltration, agroinfection, and viral infection/agroinfection). For direct administration, however, no organic creatures are employed as intermediaries. The most frequent direct approaches are protoplast transfection and biolistic particle delivery. Agroinfiltration is a transitory assay that is extensively used because of its flexibility and simplicity (116,117,118,119,120). For stable editing, agroinfection, biolistic particle delivery, and viral infection are commonly utilized. Transfection of protoplasts can be employed for both temporary and stable editing. The techniques of gene transfer utilized in plant gene editing

V. METHOD OF INDIRECTION

Agroinfiltration is the process of filtering plant pathogens such as *Agrobacterium* spp. When *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* infects plants, it creates tumor-like development on the plant's aerial portions (crown gall), whereas *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* causes root tumors. Agrobacteria include a huge plasmid (about 200 kb) called Ti in *A. tumefaciens* and Ri in *A. rhizogenes* that may transfer a particular DNA segment (transfer DNA or T-DNA) into infected plant cells, allowing the T-DNA to integrate into the host genome. These two agrobacterium strains have been altered to have a disarmed Ti/Ri plasmid with tumor-inducing genes removed. Border repeats (25 bp), one of the most important sections of T-DNA, are required for plant transformation and are employed to create transgenic plants. Agroinfiltration is a transitory experiment in which plant leaves are directly injected with an *A. tumefaciens* culture carrying mutated T-DNA (121,122,123). *A. rhizogenes* is specially employed to evaluate editing efficiency in plant root hairs for root hair transformation, and this approach has mostly been employed in legume species like *Medicago* and soybean (124,125,126).

Using the direct way

Transfection of protoplasts. Protoplast transfection is a technique for transfection and transient experiments. The cell walls of plant tissues are enzymatically digested in this approach, which then employs polyethyleneglycol (PEG) for transfection or electroporation for distribution. Several DNA constructions can be delivered by the same protoplast. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Nicotiana benthamiana*, rice, wheat, and maize, protoplast transfection has been shown to successfully transport the CRISPR/Cas system and result in gene editing (113, 127,128,129,130,131,132).

Events that are predictable

Method of indirection

Agroinfection is a disease that affects crops. For practically all model plant species, primary crop species, vegetable and fruit crops, and forest crops, agrobacterium-mediated DNA delivery is the most widely utilized approach. Agrobacterium, like agroinfiltration, may make transgenic plants by integrating its genome into the plant's nuclear DNA (133).

Infection with a virus. Tobacco mosaic virus was the first viral vector employed in plants (TMV). In *N. benthamiana*, TMV was utilized to mute a gene (134). The majority of plant viruses are RNA viruses with ssRNA genomes, which may be produced in vitro and used to inoculate plants, or they can be produced in vivo as DNA viruses from plasmids that are mechanically delivered to plants for gene delivery (135). The viral genome can be introduced as a cDNA fragment into a binary vector and then utilized for agroinfection-mediated transport into a plant cell to speed up the delivery process.

TRV (tobacco rattle virus) is a ssRNA virus with two genomic components, TRV1 (or RNA1) and TRV2 (or RNA2) (or RNA2). Inoculation necessitates the presence of both genetic components. RNA virus-edited plants do not show germline transfer of alterations. Ali et al. (136) employed agroinfection to transport the TRV RNA1 genomic component and a vector produced from TRV RNA2 containing targeting gRNA into the leaves of *N. benthamiana* overexpressing Cas9 for gene editing in plant cells.

Unlike TRV, geminiviruses do not require in vitro transcription before inoculation. The ssDNA genome of geminiviruses is circular (137). Because geminiviruses lack a gene producing DNA polymerase, their ssDNA genomes are transformed into dsDNA genomes in the nucleus by host DNA polymerases. Virus transcription and rolling circle replication are then performed using the dsDNA genome as a template. Rep (replication initiator protein) is required for rolling-circle replication to begin. SsDNA genomes can be converted to dsDNA genomes or packaged into virions via rolling circle replication. The transmission of virions to neighboring cells is facilitated by plant plasmodesmata routes (138, 139). The CRISPR/Cas system has been delivered via the bean yellow dwarf virus (BeYDV), a geminivirus (138). In tomato (anthocyanin mutant 1 gene, ANT1), gene editing using BeYDV has been demonstrated, and a modified cabbage leaf curl virus (CaLCuV) has been employed in tobacco (127, 140). Such methods have also been used in wheat, with researchers designing an improved wheat dwarf virus (WDV) system to improve the method's effectiveness (141).

Using the direct way

Transfection of protoplasts. The stable transformation strategy, in contrast to the transient protoplast transfection approach, resulted in targeted genome alterations in entire plants regenerated from gene-edited protoplasts (130, 131). The capacity to distribute many components in a large amount is one of the advantages of protoplast transfection. This approach is ideal for gene editing with donor template repair. The recovery of gene editing by donor template repair can be aided by a large number of transfected cells. The rapidity of plant regeneration in monocot plants is, however, a drawback of protoplast transfection. Potato (142), tobacco (131), and lettuce (142) have all employed protoplast transfection for gene editing.

Particles that are delivered in a biolistic manner. Transfecting cells by bombardment is used to transfer biolistic particles. Plant cells' cell walls may be pierced with physical force, allowing DNA to be delivered. Because of its efficiency and capacity to transport many DNA constructs at the same time, this approach is commonly used in converting plants (143). Most notably, biolistic particle-based delivery is not restricted to plant species. The primary downside of this approach is that, by introducing multiple copies of DNA into the target plants, unwanted effects like gene suppression may occur in the recovered transgenic plants. Using the CRISPR/Cas system, biolistic particle delivery has been exploited for gene editing in rice, wheat, soybean, and maize (144,145,146). This approach is also utilized to transfer CRISPR/Cas9 RNPs to crops like hexaploid wheat and maize for gene editing (147, 148).

Prospects for CRISPR/Cas delivery in the future

CRISPR/Cas is a basic yet flexible technology. The CRISPR/Cas system has a lot of potential for gene editing, but how CRISPR/Cas is delivered into cells has a big impact on how effective it is. There are still several components of delivery that can be enhanced to increase translatability's potential.

Immunity to the CRISPR/Cas system and the vehicle that delivers it

The Cas gene must be transported into cells in order for the Cas protein to be expressed, and the long-term and strong production of bacterially generated protein should activate the host immune system. One approach to this problem is to employ a protein-based CRISPR/Cas system delivery, which may be less immunogenic since the Cas protein is only present in the target cell for a brief time (98). When paired with the immunogenic effects generated by particular delivery vehicles, the amount of immunogenicity may render the CRISPR/Cas system ineffective. Exogenous RNA supplied by lipid nanoparticles has been shown to activate Toll-like receptors and trigger immunological responses (149). As a result, the delivery vector should be carefully selected. Furthermore, the adverse effects of viral vectors must be taken into account. AAVs and adenoviruses, in comparison to lentiviruses, can avoid the possibility of unwanted DNA integration into the host genome. The production of viral DNA or protein in host cells poses a concern for therapeutic applications (150, 151).

Biomaterials that have been engineered to improve delivery efficiency

Nonviral vectors, rather than viral vectors, may be the most suitable delivery vectors for in vivo delivery. When contrasted to viral delivery, nonviral delivery has several advantages. It minimizes the likelihood of off-target effects by shortening the nuclease expression time and allows for better dosage duration control (90). The rise and development of nanotechnology and material sciences has resulted in a wide range of gene editing applications. Gold-based nanoparticles have been proven to deliver RNP effectively both in vitro and in vivo (100). Furthermore, polymeric-and lipid-based nanoparticles have minimal immunogenicity, particularly when it comes to encapsulating big cargos (152). Furthermore, PEI-magnetic nanoparticles have recently been proven to increase CRISPR/Cas9 construct distribution in vitro with low cell toxicity and to be a potential delivery strategy that can increase the safety and usability of gene editing (153, 154). Furthermore, utilizing the nanoneedle array technique, researchers demonstrated direct transport of the Cas9 RNP complex into cells, with gene disruption efficiencies of roughly 32 percent and 16 percent in HeLa cells and mouse breast cancer cells, respectively. Although the efficiency might be increased, researchers were able to effectively show gene editing by utilizing a nanoneedle array to deliver Cas9/sgRNA, and this technique of delivery might be used for HDR gene knock-in (155). Chen et al. recently revealed a gene editing platform made up of vertically aligned silicon nanotube (VA-SiNT) arrays. They effectively transported Cas9 RNP to the target gene and exhibited SiNT-facilitated biocargo internalization with an efficiency of more than 80%. This suggested that the molecular transport platform provided by nanotubes has a lot of potential for advancing gene-editing technologies (156). However, there are still obstacles to nanoparticle-mediated protein delivery, such as the laborious process of packing into tailored materials and preventing RNP breakdown before it penetrates the nucleus. To transfer cargos to the nucleus for successful gene editing, biocompatible, well-tolerated, high-capability, and nonimmunogenic delivery vehicles are necessary, and these properties are crucial for developing any nonviral delivery material.

Cas9 activity is regulated both spatially and temporally.

As previously stated, the CRISPR/Cas system's unintentional off-target impact is a big worry. It's crucial to control the delivery of CRISPR/Cas system components to certain target locations before Cas9 is switched on, as well as the delivery of particular elements that turn on this machinery at a given moment. Cas9 endonuclease inhibitors have been discovered by several groups. Anti-CRISPR (Acr) proteins like AcrIIA4 can stop Cas9 from working (157, 158). Anti-CRISPRs might also be employed to restrict editing to specific cells and tissues in the body. Researchers created miRNA-responsive Acr switches, and using Cas9 or dCas9 to deploy this machinery permitted tissue-specific editing (159). Researchers created ProCas9 Cas9 variants that allowed the CRISPR/Cas9 system to be turned on exclusively in target cells in a recent

study (160). ProCas9 uses proteases to determine the sort of cell it is in. This mechanism allows for a safer translation of CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing, and this technique might be utilized to assist plants resist viral infections.

Several methods for regulating Cas9 activity or expression have also been established. Cas9 has been found to be expressed in two forms: split (161,162,163,164) and inactive (165, 166). Furthermore, an inducible mechanism allowed Cas9 to be activated only when it was triggered by a chemical inducer (167,168,169,170,171) or exposed to certain wavelengths of light (164). Cas9 activity is only triggered when the two domains of Cas9, the recognition domain and the nuclease domain, are assembled, according to research (172). This split-Cas9 technique is also used for intein-based gene editing. Protein introns extract themselves from host polypeptides to produce a functional protein (173). The split Cas9 system based on intein sequences is made up of split Cas9 domains fused to intein sequences. These intein sequences will be spliced out after dimerization, resulting in fully active Cas9 (161). Cas9 domains may be supplied independently by AAV vectors and have similar editing efficiencies as full-length Cas9, according to Truong et al. (161). Exposure to rapamycin, which promotes FK506-binding protein (FKBP)-FKBP rapamycin binding (FRB) dimerization, can also chemically stimulate Cas9 (174). Split Cas9 fragments coupled with FRB and FKBP fragments make up rapamycin-inducible split-Cas9. A fully active Cas9 is generated in the presence of rapamycin. Photoactivatable Cas9 (paCas9) was also achieved using photoinducible dimerizing protein domains known as Magnets (164). By fusing each Cas9 fragment with magnet fragments (pMagnet and nMagnet) and initiating magnet dimerization with blue light treatment, this optically controlled split-Cas9 system was created (175). Several alternative optically controlled methods for CRISPR/Cas-based transcriptional activation and gene editing have also been disclosed (175,176,177,178). A light-inducible mechanism was created by Nihongaki et al. They combined integrin binding protein 1 (CIB1) with dCas9 and cryptochrome 2 (CRY2) with a transcriptional activator domain, then employed blue light to cause CIB1 and CRY2 to dimerize, resulting in downstream target expression (175). Shao et al. created a FRL-activated CRISPR/dCas9 effector (FACE) system based on dCas9 (179,180,181) and the bacterial phytochrome BphS (182), which triggered transcription of target genes in the presence of FRL (178).

CRISPR/Cas9 systems may also be regulated in a tunable manner in other ways. To modulate protein stability, Wandless and coworkers utilized tiny cell-permeable compounds. By fusing molecules to a destabilizing domain, this chemical-genetic method allows for fast and controllable production of a particular protein (183). The destabilizing domain functions as a degron, directing the fusion protein to proteasome-dependent degradation in the absence of a small molecule ligand, allowing for variable protein function regulation. The fusion protein is protected from degradation by ligand attachment to the destabilizing domain, allowing the protein of interest to function properly. Shield-1 with mutant K506-binding protein (FKBP) 12 destabilized domain (FKBP (DD)), trimethoprim with mutant dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) destabilized domain (DHFR (DD)), and CMP8 with the 4-OHT-estrogen receptor destabilized domain (ER50 (DD)) are among the ligand-destabilizing domain pairs discovered so far (183,184,185). Switchable gene editing and activation may be achieved using this technique (186,187,188). Drug inducible gene editing was achieved by fusing FKBP (DD), DHFR (DD), and ER50 (DD) to Cas9 (187, 188).

For drug inducible gene activation, DHFR (DD) or ER50 (DD) were joined to the PP7-activation domain (179), and DHFR (DD) can be fused directly to the dCas9 activator (186). Various ligand-destabilizing domain pairs can be paired with different aptamers to create multidimensional control (187). Another platform uses the nonstructural protein 3 (NS3) protease domain of the hepatitis C virus (HCV) and its different inhibitors to modulate CRISPR/Cas activity (189). The NS3 protease domain was incorporated into dCas9-VPR by Tague et al. to create a ligand-inducible CRISPR activation platform (189, 190). To generate a dCas9-NS3-NLS-VPR complex, the NS3 protease domain was inserted between the DNA binding scaffold and the C-terminal region, which contains NLS and VPR. Separation of VPR from dCas9 by NS3 protease inhibits transcriptional activation, whereas transcriptional activation is accomplished in the presence of a protease inhibitor. Cas9 has recently been coupled with the HCV NS3 and nonstructural protein 4a-based small molecule-assisted shut-off tag (SMASH) (NS4A, acting as a degron). SMASH can regulate Cas9 stability with asunaprevir, an HCV protease inhibitor. When NS3-NS4A is blocked in the presence of asunaprevir, Cas9 protein is destroyed, but in the absence of asunaprevir, Cas9 gene editing activity is restored (191-274).

Unfortunately, certain roadblocks remain in the way of implementing the regulatory approach to the CRISPR/Cas system. Chemical inducers may cause cytotoxicity, making in vivo implementation of this method more problematic. Furthermore, light-induced systems may be confined to in vitro investigations since activating such a system in vivo would be invasive, and light penetration into tissue might cause other issues. To further the clinical translation of the CRISPR/Cas system, further research, optimization, and development is required to overcome these obstacles.

VI. CONCLUSION

The discovery and implementation of the CRISPR/Cas system holds considerable promise for the treatment of human diseases and the revolutionization of plant breeding. Despite the fact that research on the CRISPR/Cas system is well underway in the life sciences community, there are still significant challenges to efficient delivery that must be solved in order to accomplish successful gene editing. When choosing a strategy, consider factors such as specificity, effectiveness, and controllable expression. Many of the drawbacks of the CRISPR/Cas system's translatability have been solved thanks to the development of novel delivery mechanisms. With the fast advancement of delivery techniques, a successful translation of CRISPR/Cas technology into medical and agricultural uses is critical, and significant advancements are expected.

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